

Interest/Influence Matrix

TOOLSHEET

Purpose

Exercise to reflect on the position of partners/stakeholders in terms of influence and interest and how to engage them. To be used iteratively throughout the proposal preparation/project to assess and improve participant and stakeholder collaborative relationships.

Benefits

- help identify crucial stakeholders or boost/undermine the innovation according to their influence/interest
- monitor the role of stakeholders according to their influence/interest and adapt the project strategy and activities accordingly.

Practical recommendations

Step 1 – Introduction (5 min)

In case of a workshop focussing on this tool: explain the purpose, logic and background of the exercise. Depending on whether the initiator wishes to involve different types of partners/stakeholders or not, the exercise may be participatory or not.

Step 2 – Identification of stakeholders (30 min)

Alone or together, identify different stakeholder categories, and reflect on the actor category you/the group are representing in the project.

The types of stakeholders that should be taken into account are typically cited in calls, as a credential of the project's multi-actor approach.

Step 3 – Collective agreement (20 min)

Should this exercise be participatory, all participants should reflect on the position of the different stakeholders within the matrix and collective agreement is to be found.

Step 4 – Use/re-evaluate/expand (x min)

Use the matrix to design and substantiate a project strategy. This matrix can be re-evaluated or expanded during the course of the project.

Credit: Sylvain Quiédeville, & Robert Home. (2022). LIAISON Evaluation & Impact Assessment Tool: #27 Interest - influence matrix. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6412327>

Applicability box

Main MA Skills supported

Active participation of, and focus on end-users

Balance needs of both yourself and the consortium as a whole

Relevant Target groups

Useful link(s)*

[Link to download the materials](#)

*right click to open

Figure 1: Interest/influence matrix